

Teens using pharmacogenomics for personalized hypertension medication

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Topic: Pharmacogenomics

Title: Teens using pharmacogenomics for personalized hypertension medication

Objectives: To explore the current literature on pharmacogenomic testing for adolescent hypertension treatments in order to support improved treatment outcomes. We aim to improve health literacy through research on pharmacogenomic testing for teen hypertension.

Background: Nearly 1 in 4 teens in the United States have high blood pressure or are nearly at risk for it, according to the CDC. Most clinical trials for gene therapy to help treat high blood pressure have been done on adults, not teens. Today, high blood pressure is usually treated by implementing different drugs to see what works, and pharmacogenomics could help by showing which drugs work best for each type of person. Identifying research needs for teens will help show if the treatments are safe and effective for them and not just adults.

Methods: To analyze the literature, we conducted a Web of Science Core Collection search using specific keywords, including *pharmacogenomics*, *hypertension*, *adolescents*, and *personalized treatment plans*. We then reviewed each article and excluded those unrelated to our research question, such as articles on *chronic heart failure*, *kidney disease*, *elderly populations*, and other irrelevant topics, leaving 100 articles that specifically focused on genetic testing and treatment outcomes for teenage hypertension.

Results: After analyzing the 100 selected articles' key terms, the most common terms were *polymorphisms* (52 references), *disease* (51 references), *variant* (39 references), *pharmacogenomics* (28 references), and *influencing* (21 references). Other commonly used terms included *protocol*, *outcomes*, *patients*, *genes*, and *individualize*, all of which appeared more than 15 times. The terms were commonly linked to genetic variation, personalized medicine, and hypertension treatment.

Conclusions: We need more research on how using pharmacogenomics can help make better treatment plans for teens. Several studies show how specific genetic markers, like CYP2D6 and ACE gene variations are current research focuses of how people respond to common hypertension treatment and medicines.

Keyword 1: Pharmacogenomics

Keyword 2: Hypertension

Keyword 3: Teenagers

Keyword 4: Personalized Treatment Plan

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